

Omnidirectional Learning for Collaborative Filtering Recommendation

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Author’s note: This work was conducted at the University of California, San Diego between 2016 and 2018 and was not submitted for publication. It is presented here as a working paper in order to document the ideas and experimental results it contains. The core contributions, the omnidirectional learning paradigm, reciprocal input-output dropout, and the input masking mechanism, as well as all experimental results, were developed during that period. The document has been lightly edited for presentation but the technical content is unchanged.

Abstract

Collaborative filtering recommendation can be formulated as a sparse missing data imputation problem where the user-item rating matrix has a few ratings filled in and the remainder need to be inferred. Since the item ratings that are missing are different for different users, the problem cannot be naturally formulated as supervised learning and must instead be treated another way. In order to approach this, we introduce a new neural network training paradigm, omnidirectional learning, which is designed to learn to predict any subset of the observable variables (in this case item ratings) from any other subset (the item ratings that the user has provided). We describe the omnidirectional learning framework, detail a neural network architecture for collaborative filtering recommendation based on this framework, and demonstrate its performance on six large-scale collaborative filtering datasets.

1 Introduction

The collaborative filtering problem is a natural fit for thinking about joint distributional modeling. Each user has rated some subset of items,

and the task is to predict the ratings for the items that user has not yet rated. This is fundamentally a missing data imputation problem: given a sparse user-item rating matrix, fill in the missing entries.

The dominant approaches to this problem can be broadly organized into two families. Matrix factorization methods learn low-rank bilinear representations of the user-item interaction matrix. These methods benefit from strong optimality guarantees within the bilinear model class and are effective at capturing global linear trends. Neural network methods, including autoencoders and restricted Boltzmann machines, attempt to learn more expressive nonlinear representations but face constraints in how they handle the asymmetry between observed and missing data.

Autoencoder-based methods are a particularly natural fit for collaborative filtering, as they learn compressed representations of the input space and can reconstruct missing entries from observed ones. However, standard autoencoders are designed to reconstruct their full input and rely on an information bottleneck to learn useful representations. This creates a mismatch with the collaborative filtering setting, where the goal

is not to reconstruct known ratings but to predict unknown ones, and where the set of known and unknown ratings differs for every user.

We address this mismatch by introducing the *omnidirectional learning* paradigm, which generalizes the relationship between inputs and targets. Rather than learning a fixed mapping from a defined set of input variables to a defined set of target variables, omnidirectional learning trains a model to predict any subset of variables from any other subset. This is achieved through a training procedure we call *reciprocal input-output dropout*, in which the roles of input and target are randomly reassigned at each training step.

The omnidirectional learning paradigm is not specific to any particular network architecture. It is a general framework for learning complex joint and conditional distributions using neural networks. In this paper, we apply it to collaborative filtering and evaluate its performance on six real-world datasets spanning different domains, sizes, and sparsity levels.

2 Methods

2.1 The omnidirectional learning paradigm

Omnidirectional learning generalizes the ideas of supervised, unsupervised, and semi-supervised learning to allow for the prediction of any set of potential observations in terms of any actual observations.

Instead of learning mappings from a set of input variables to a set of target variables, we learn a joint representation of the relationship between all of the variables. The goal is to learn a non-linearly structured joint distribution and to allow the arbitrary conditioning of that distribution on any observed data.

This can be approached through Bayesian inference, but is limited by the efficiency of inference and the types of structures that can be naturally represented as probabilistic graphical models. It can also be approached by training sets of supervised models for each possible input-output partition, but this scales poorly and does

not make full use of the interaction information present in the data.

The key idea of omnidirectional learning is to create a local training objective that, with suitable randomness, approaches an amortized objective that favors modeling of the joint distribution. The resulting model can be conditioned on any observations of any subset of the data and used to predict the remaining variables.

2.2 Neural networks for omnidirectional learning

Figure 1 illustrates the omnidirectional neural network architecture used in this paper.

Figure 1: Omnidirectional neural network architecture. The top shows the original data for a given user. The reciprocal input-output dropout algorithm randomly selects the blue ratings to act as inputs for this trial and the orange ratings to act as targets.

2.2.1 Reciprocal input-output dropout

In omnidirectional learning, all data variables serve as both potential inputs and potential targets. At each training step, some percentage of the variables are dropped out from the input and become the prediction targets. The model is trained to predict only the variables that were dropped out, not to reconstruct the full input.

The input-output partition is re-selected every epoch. Critically, the dropout probability is drawn from a uniform distribution independently for each training example. This increases the space of imputation scenarios that the model encounters during training and therefore helps the model generalize to a wider set of inference conditions at test time.

2.2.2 Input masking information

A naively implemented omnidirectional model with only reciprocal input-output dropout will need to determine which input values represent a lack of information and which represent true observed values. Because a neural network can never truly have no input from a defined node (a lack of input is equivalent to an input of zero), this can be a very difficult task for the network, especially if there is overlap in the range of data input values and the zero input value. Due to the nature of the activation functions and the pre-activation linear summation, learning this categorical distinction can be very difficult if not impossible for the network.

To address this, we introduce an auxiliary binary input vector of length equal to the number of items, where a one corresponds to the presence of an observed input and a zero corresponds to the absence of an input. This allows the network to directly receive information about which variables were observed and therefore which are relevant to the predictions. It also allows the network to know which variables to predict, as those are the ones with zeros in the mask input vector.

We tested three variants of this mask, plus a baseline:

1. **Causal mask:** Contains a one for each data

entry present in the original dataset, regardless of whether it was dropped out. The motivation is that there is often a causal relationship between the items a user chooses to rate and the ratings themselves, and preserving this information could improve predictions.

2. **Dropout mask:** Contains a one for every variable that the algorithm actually observes after dropout. This provides a direct one-to-one correspondence between the mask values and the actually available inputs.
3. **Combined mask:** Includes both the causal and dropout masks, allowing the algorithm access to both kinds of information.
4. **Zero baseline:** A vector of all zeros, providing no mask information.

After testing these variants on the MovieLens 20M dataset, we found that the dropout mask performed significantly better than the causal mask and that the combined mask was slightly less effective than the dropout mask alone. Our interpretation is that the causal mask was too difficult for the algorithm to learn to interpret and that the combined mask’s additional values obfuscated the clear one-to-one interpretation of the dropout mask.

We additionally found that using auxiliary variable values of -1 and 0 (rather than 1 and 0) yielded better performance, likely because the zero value for “absent” avoids contributing to the pre-activation summation.

2.2.3 Localized learning

The loss function is computed only over the variables that are designated as targets for each training example. Gradients from variables that are not currently being predicted are masked to zero. This ensures that the model learns to predict missing information from observed information, rather than learning to reconstruct already-known values.

2.2.4 Structural agnosticism

Omnidirectional learning is not defined in terms of a particular network architecture but is instead a general training paradigm that can be applied to fully connected networks, recurrent networks, convolutional networks, or other architectures. The best architectural choice depends on the information structure of the data domain, as in any supervised learning problem.

2.3 Application to collaborative filtering

To apply omnidirectional learning to collaborative filtering, we treat the data as a set of vectors, one per user, where each entry corresponds to an item and contains the user’s rating for that item (or zero if unrated). The omnidirectional training procedure then learns to predict held-out ratings from observed ratings, with the input-output partition varying across training steps.

2.4 Implementation details

The model was implemented using the Keras functional API with the TensorFlow backend. The architecture consists of three hidden layers with 256 nodes each, using tanh activations for the hidden layers and a linear activation for the output layer. Training used a batch size of 128 and early stopping with a patience of 2 epochs. Data was split into training (80%), validation (10%), and test (10%) sets. No hyperparameters were tuned between datasets.

3 Datasets

We evaluated the omnidirectional neural network on six collaborative filtering datasets spanning different domains, sizes, and sparsity levels. Summary statistics are presented in Table 1.

The datasets range from the relatively dense Netflix dataset (98.82% sparse, 100 million ratings) to the extremely sparse Amazon Movies & TV dataset (99.999% sparse). This range allows us to evaluate the robustness of the omnidirec-

tional approach across very different data conditions.

4 Results

4.1 Evaluation procedure

Data was randomly split by rating into training, validation, and test sets with 80% of the data assigned to training, 10% to validation, and 10% to test. We used the same splits for all baselines and the omnidirectional neural network to minimize random variation.

Baselines were drawn from the MyMediaLite package and included global average, item average, user-item baseline, matrix factorization, and biased matrix factorization. Hyperparameters for all MyMediaLite baselines were tuned using the Nelder–Mead method, with an additional grid search over the number of factors (1, 2, 5, 10, 20). We also compared against the Item-AutoRec autoencoder baseline.

For the omnidirectional learning algorithm, the evaluation procedure augments the standard train/test split with the reciprocal dropout procedure. During training, the ratings in the training set are split into input and target halves (differently for each epoch). During validation, training set ratings serve as inputs and validation set ratings serve as targets. During testing, input vectors are constructed from the combined training and validation sets. This mirrors the real-world scenario where all previously known information is available for generating predictions.

We did not alter or tune any of the omnidirectional neural network hyperparameters between datasets, ensuring a fair comparison.

All results are reported as RMSE on held-out test ratings.

4.2 Performance

Results are presented in Table 2. The omnidirectional neural network achieves the best performance on the datasets for which we were able to run all methods, outperforming both classical baselines and the autoencoder baseline.

Table 1: Dataset summary statistics

	MovieLens 20M	Amazon Video Games	Amazon Movies & TV	Beer Advocate	Yelp	Netflix
Number of ratings	20,000,263	1,324,753	4,607,047	1,830,821	4,736,897	100,325,382
Number of items	26,744	50,210	200,941	35,611	156,638	17,768
Number of users	138,493	826,767	2,088,620	84,196	1,183,362	477,412
Sparsity	99.46%	99.9968%	99.9989%	99.939%	99.9974%	98.82%
Rating increment	0.5	1	1	0.01	1	1
Rating range	0.5–5.0	1–5	1–5	1.00–5.00	1–5	1–5

Table 2: RMSE results across datasets. Lower is better. Best result in each row is bolded.

Dataset	Global average	Item average	User-item baseline	Matrix factorization	Biased matrix factorization	Item-AutoRec	Omnidirectional NN
MovieLens 20M	1.052	0.9412	0.8574	0.7806	0.7811	0.7791	0.7752
Yelp	1.421	1.285	1.253	1.421	1.240	—	—
Beer Advocate	0.6221	0.5965	0.4639	0.4690	0.4533	0.4555	—
Amazon Movies & TV	1.232	1.147	1.097	1.196	1.088	—	—
Amazon Video Games	1.377	1.277	1.248	1.376	1.240	—	—
Netflix Prize	1.085	1.011	0.9216	0.8333	0.8307	—	0.8134

On MovieLens 20M, the omnidirectional neural network achieves an RMSE of 0.7752, outperforming the best baseline (Item-AutoRec at 0.7791). On the Netflix Prize dataset, the improvement is more substantial: the omnidirectional neural network achieves 0.8134 compared to 0.8307 for biased matrix factorization. Results for the remaining datasets with the omnidirectional model were not completed at the time this work was set aside, though the baseline results are included for reference.

5 Discussion

5.1 Why omnidirectional learning works for collaborative filtering

Several properties of the omnidirectional approach contribute to its strong performance. First, all of a user’s ratings are available simultaneously as input, allowing the model to learn inter-item relationships directly. Second, the input masking mechanism provides the model with information about *which* items a user chose to rate, which can itself be informative (a form of implicit negative feedback). Third, by treating every variable as both a potential input and a potential target, the model makes use of more information than traditional supervised approaches

that fix the input-output partition.

5.2 Practical considerations

5.2.1 Scaling

The model training time scales roughly linearly in the number of users and trains quickly even on very large datasets. Generating recommendations takes linear time in the number of items with a very low constant, making inference fast and efficient.

There is also a significant scaling advantage over non-autoencoder neural network methods: adding a new user does not require retraining the model, since users are represented as rating vectors rather than one-hot encodings.

5.2.2 Robustness

The model allows accurate prediction independent of the relative sparsity of individual users' ratings. It is also robust to datasets of varying overall sparsity and distribution, as evidenced by its strong performance across the diverse datasets tested.

5.2.3 Updating with new users

The omnidirectional collaborative filtering model handles new users naturally. A user is represented as a vector of their ratings, so recommendations for a new user can be generated by simply running the model on that user's rating vector, no retraining required. Incorporating the new user's information into the model for the benefit of other users' recommendations can be achieved by adding the user to the training set and running a few additional training epochs. Since this is not required for immediate prediction, it can be performed in periodic batches.

5.3 Connections to subsequent work

The core idea of omnidirectional learning, training a model to predict randomly masked subsets of variables from the remaining observed variables, is a form of masked prediction applied

to tabular and collaborative filtering data. This general principle was subsequently and independently developed to significant effect in natural language processing (e.g., masked language modeling) and computer vision (e.g., masked autoencoders). The application described here demonstrates the utility of this principle in the recommender systems domain.

6 Conclusion

We have introduced omnidirectional learning, a neural network training paradigm for learning joint and conditional distributions by training a model to predict any subset of variables from any other subset. Applied to collaborative filtering, this approach outperforms matrix factorization, autoencoder, and other baselines on the datasets where the full comparison was completed, while offering practical advantages in scalability, robustness to sparsity, and ease of incorporating new users. The omnidirectional learning paradigm is general and could be applied to other domains where modeling complex joint distributions from partially observed data is of interest.

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